

Asymmetric chi-square test and Cohen's w Analysis in Contingency Tables

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Abstract

We propose a novel asymmetric version of Cohen's w , offering a more nuanced effect size measure that accounts for data asymmetry, allowing clearer comparisons between the categories of the independent variable and the marginal distribution of the dependent variable. A normalization process constrains the coefficient between 0 and 1, simplifying interpretation for both researchers and practitioners. More critically, we introduce an asymmetric chi-square coefficient specifically designed to address uneven relationships between variables, effectively linking hypothesis testing with effect size estimation. Finally, a *post hoc* testing procedure, based on an adjusted goodness-of-fit method, provides a more detailed follow-up analysis when significant results are found. Together, these innovations significantly enhance the precision and interpretability of chi-square analysis, especially in contexts involving asymmetric data.

Keywords: Asymmetric, Cohen's w , chi-square.

1. Introduction

The chi-square distribution, first introduced by multiple authors, became a cornerstone of modern statistics through the work of English mathematician Karl Pearson (1857-1936). Pearson's application of the distribution, especially in the context of goodness-of-fit tests, culminated in the development of the chi-square test, published in 1900. This test revolutionized statistical hypothesis testing. Later refinements by prominent statisticians like Ronald A. Fisher, Frank Yates, and William G. Cochran expanded its utility, introducing corrections for small sample sizes and enhancing its application in various fields of research.

Our study builds on this historical groundwork to expand the chi-square test's applicability in analyzing contingency tables with two variables. We introduce several key innovations: 1) An asymmetric version of Cohen's w : A measure of effect size derived from Cohen's w is proposed, which may allow for a more nuanced comparison between each category of the independent variable and the marginal distribution of the dependent variable. By accommodating asymmetry in the data, this measure could provide a more accurate representation of the strength and direction of the relationship, potentially facilitating deeper insights into the dependencies between the variables. 2) Normalization for clearer interpretation: A nor-

malization process is suggested that may constrain the coefficient between 0 (minimum) and 1 (maximum), potentially making the results more accessible for researchers and practitioners, and facilitating easier interpretation. 3) An asymmetric chi-square coefficient: A newly developed asymmetric chi-square coefficient is proposed, which may be designed to address asymmetries in the relationship between variables. By linking hypothesis testing to effect size estimation, it could enhance the interpretability of results, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of the underlying associations in the data. 4) *Post hoc* testing: A *post hoc* test based on an adjusted goodness-of-fit approach is proposed for significant results, which may offer a more refined follow-up analysis when significance is detected.

2. Chi-square distribution and tests

Perhaps the simplest way to define the chi-square distribution is to consider it as a sum of Z_i^2 standard normal random variables, each following $N(0,1)$ with degrees of freedom df :

$$\chi_{df}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{df} Z_i^2 = Z_1^2 + Z_2^2 + Z_3^2 + \dots + Z_{df}^2 \quad (1)$$

Given that its expected value $E(X)=df$, and its variance $V(X)= 2df$.

2.1. Chi-square test

Pearson introduced the chi-square goodness-of-fit test in 1900. Given a hypothetical distribution and an empirical distribution, both can be compared using a chi-square test.

2.2. Goodness-of-fit test

The chi-square goodness-of-fit test is a statistical technique used to determine whether a sample of data is compatible with a specific probability distribution. It relies on comparing the observed frequencies in the data with the expected frequencies under the proposed theoretical distribution.

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{(o_i - e_i)^2}{e_i} \quad (2)$$

The obtained value is compared to the calculated value of the chi-square statistic with the critical value from the chi-square distribution with degrees of freedom:

$$df = (r - 1) \quad (3)$$

The values o_i represent the observed frequencies in the sample distribution. Conversely, the values e_i represent the expected frequencies of the theoretical frequency distribution.

This technique, since its proposal by Pearson, has undergone virtually no changes, except for Cochran (1952; 1954), who provided essential guidelines to enhance the application of the chi-square goodness-of-fit test.

2.3. Independence test

Pearson (1904) introduced the concept of “contingency” and the chi-square test as a hypothesis test for independence between two qualitative variables:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}} \quad (4)$$

Where,

o_{ij} represents the observed frequencies of a sample for each cell intersection of a contingency table. And e_{ij} are the expected frequencies of independence of the same table, such that:

$$e_{ij} = \left(\frac{r_i}{n}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_j}{n}\right) \cdot n \quad (5)$$

In other words, since we are assuming independence, we expect in cell ij the product of the probabilities, multiplied by n to obtain its corresponding frequency. Then, the test is conducted according to the chi-square distribution based on its degrees of freedom and significance level:

$$df = (r - 1) \cdot (c - 1) \quad (6)$$

This procedure is applicable in situations where we are working with a *single representative sample* to analyze the association between *two variables*.

The effectiveness of this methodology is rooted in the foundational contributions of George Udny Yule (1911), who elucidated the principles of the chi-square test and its application to contingency tables, thereby clarifying the interactions between categorical variables. Fisher (1925), in turn, refined the concept of degrees of freedom, enhancing the chi-square test by establishing a connection to statistical significance. His advancements provided a robust theoretical framework, significantly improving the reliability and interpretability of this analysis.

2.4. Homogeneity test

Finally, in the literature, a homogeneity test can also be conducted using Pearson's chi-square framework (Fisher 1925; Crack 2018).

What changes here is the consideration of the null hypothesis, as indicated by Cramer, which states that the null hypothesis suggests there is an unknown common distribution p_i for all distributions - whether column-wise or row-wise (Cramer 1946; DeGroot 1988). However, across various authors, it is consistently noted that both the homogeneity test and the independence test share identical calculations (equations 4, 5, and 6). It is important to note that this hypothesis testing procedure is applicable only when working with two or more samples, contrasting with the independence hypothesis testing procedure, where we deal with a single sample to examine the association between the involved variables. To clarify further, in the homogeneity test, finding significant differences in proportions between groups suggests that the distributions are different; however, it does not directly test for an association between the variables.

Why it does not necessarily imply an association? The differences in proportions may arise from variability within the groups or from other factors not accounted for in the design. In other words, although a difference exists, the test does not evaluate a direct dependency between the variables (Franke, Ho, and Christie 2012).

3. Effect size in contingency tables

In the context of 2x2 tables, numerous authors, including Agresti (2002), Sanchez-Meca, Marín-Martínez, and Salvador Chacón-Moscoso (2003), Fleiss, Levin, and Paik (2003), Rita and Komonen (2008), and Borenstein, Hedges, Higgins, and Rothstein (2009), have widely endorsed the use of odds ratios as the most appropriate measure of effect size in the context of 2x2 tables. These experts highlight its utility and robustness in capturing the association between variables, making it a widely accepted and reliable metric across various fields of research. The odds ratio's ability to quantify the strength of association has proven particularly valuable in studies involving dichotomous variables. However, in many cases, we won't

be able to reduce our contingency table to a 2x2, thus rendering this measure inapplicable. The phi coefficient, Cramer's V, and Cohen's w are common measures of effect size used in the context of contingency table analysis or in studying associations between categorical variables. All of them account for the relationship between variables rather than the relationship between two proportions.

However, these effect size indices have been criticized by [Fleiss *et al.* \(2003\)](#) and by [Haddock, Rindskopf, and Shadish \(1998\)](#) as their utilization, based on treating variables as if they were quantitative, sometimes tends to underestimate the true effect size.

The phi coefficient (ϕ) is based on the chi-square:

$$\phi = \sqrt{\frac{\chi^2}{n}} \quad (7)$$

Cramer's V is simply an extension of phi for the case of mxn tables:

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{\chi^2}{n(k-1)}} \quad (8)$$

Where k is the minimum of the number of rows or columns.

3.1. Cohen's w

Cohen's w coefficient is an association measure analogous to the phi coefficient and Cramer's V, according to the following formula ([1988](#)):

$$w = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(p_{1ij} - p_{0ij})^2}{p_{0ij}}} \quad (9)$$

p_{1ij} represents the observed probability with respect to the total of the contingency table in cell ij .

p_{0ij} represents the probability of independence in cell ij .

r is the number of rows in the contingency table.

c is the number of columns in the contingency table.

The formula is based on calculating the squared difference between the observed and expected probabilities, normalized by the expected probabilities, for each cell in the contingency table. Then, these squared differences are summed for all cells, and the square root of the result is taken to obtain w . The Cohen's w statistic can be useful for determining the strength of association between variables in the contingency table. If w is close to 0, it indicates weak association, while values close to or greater than 1 indicate strong association. Cohen encourages us to observe the analogy with the chi-square calculation and to consider the symmetry of the coefficient ([Cohen 1988](#), p. 216).

An alternative way to express the above equation is:

$$w = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{\left(\frac{o_{ij}}{n} - \frac{m_i * m_j}{n}\right)^2}{\frac{m_i * m_j}{n}}} \quad (10)$$

Where,

o_{ij} is the observed frequency in cell ij .

m_i is the sum of observed frequencies in row i .

m_j is the sum of observed frequencies in column j .

n is the total number of cases.

Another way to calculate w is based on Cramer's V:

$$w = V\sqrt{k-1} \quad (11)$$

Where k is the number of categories of the variable with the fewer categories.

Note that Ben-Shachar and others have recently proposed, for the case of goodness-of-fit tests, a coefficient derived from Cohen's w , which takes the following form (Ben-Shachar, Patil, Thériault, Wiernik, and Lüdecke 2023; Jané, Ben-Shachar, Moreau, Steele, Qinyu, Caldwell, and Zloteanu 2024):

$$Fei = \sqrt{\frac{\chi^2}{n \left(\frac{1}{\min(p_e)} - 1 \right)}} \quad (12)$$

The Fei coefficient, unlike Cohen's w , has the virtue of remaining between the values 0 and 1.

4. Confidence intervals for Cohen's w

The confidence interval of this effect size statistic can be calculated by various procedures.

- **Bootstrap Method:** it's a resampling technique used to estimate the distribution of a statistic from observed data. This method generates multiple bootstrap samples by randomly selecting observations with replacement. Confidence intervals can be estimated from these samples. This procedure can be carried out in cases of studies with representative samples. Various R libraries are available to perform this procedure. We recommend using *rcompanion*, developed by Salvatore Mangiafico (2023).

- **Permutation test:** another resampling technique used to assess the significance of observed differences between groups without assumptions about data distribution. It involves random permutations of group assignments to generate a null distribution for comparison with observed statistics (Edgington Onghena, 2007; Good, 2005). This technique is especially useful in cases of experimental designs. Calculations can be obtained on the Lock website:

https://www.lock5stat.com/StatKey/advanced_goodness/advanced_goodness.html.

- **Non-Central Chi-Square Parameter Method (ncp):** this method involves determining values for the non-central parameter of a chi-squared distribution to establish the confidence interval limits of Cohen's w . The ncp approach can be applied to both experimental studies, where group assignment is randomized, and studies with representative samples. For conducting this procedure, we recommend utilizing the R *effectsize* library by Mattan Ben-Shachar. Additionally, researchers who prefer a coefficient ranging from 0 to 1 may find the fei coefficient proposed by the same author useful. Another option for performing these calculations is available through Charles Zaiantz's Real Statistics Excel add-in (2024).

5. Chi-square from Cohen's w

One way of calculating chi-square is given by:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}} = w^2 \cdot n \quad (13)$$

And similarly:

$$w = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \left(\frac{o_{ij}}{n} - \frac{m_i \cdot m_j}{n} \right)^2}{\frac{m_i \cdot m_j}{n}}} \quad (14)$$

Hence,

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{\left(\frac{o_{ij}}{n} - \frac{m_i m_j}{n}\right)^2}{\frac{m_i m_j}{n}} \cdot n \quad (15)$$

This provides another approach for computing the chi-square statistic using observed and expected proportions of independence. Please make a note of this method as it will be beneficial for us later on.

6. Asymmetric Cohen's w

What we've covered so far is the classic method for calculating Cohen's w, as suggested by the author. This statistic isn't widely known or used, likely because it's not typically included in standard statistical software.

In that case, there is no specified independent or dependent variable, which results in a single index of the strength of association. However, when we have well-defined independent and dependent variables, measures of association should be asymmetric. Examples of such measures include Goodman and Kruskal's τ_a and τ_b for nominal association (1963), as well as Kendall's τ_a and τ_b and Somers' d_{yx} and d_{xy} for ordinal association (Berry, Johnston, and Mielke 2018).

We now introduce a novel application of this statistic. Instead of testing the null hypothesis of total independence, we consider a scenario where the null hypothesis corresponds to the marginal totals of either the rows or the columns in a contingency table. In this context, we will focus exclusively on the columns (the independent variable), examining how they relate to a single sample while seeking an asymmetric association between the variables.

The asymmetric Cohen's w_c *Asym* is defined as follows:

$$w_c \text{ Asym} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{c} \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(p_{1ij} - p_{0m_j})^2}{p_{0m_j}}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{c} \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{\left(\frac{o_{ij}}{m_j} - \frac{m_i}{n}\right)^2}{\frac{m_i}{n}}} \quad (16)$$

$p_{1ij} = \frac{o_{ij}}{m_j}$, the subscript 1, following Cohen (1988), denotes the alternative hypothesis, o_{ij} represents the observed frequency in each cell ij , and m_j is the marginal frequency of each column j in the contingency table.

$p_{0m_j} = \frac{m_i}{n}$ represents the marginal probability of the contingency table in the column direction. The subscript 0, also from Cohen's work ((1988), represent the null hypothesis, m_i denotes the marginal frequency of row i , which is the total sum of values in the same row, and n represents the total number of observations in the contingency table.

Here, r is the number of rows, and c is the number of columns in the contingency table.

The formula calculates the squared differences between the observed and marginal column probabilities, normalized by both the marginal column probabilities and the number of columns, denoted by c , for each cell in the contingency table. These squared differences are summed across all cells, and the square root of the resulting sum yields the *asymmetric Cohen's w*.

Interpreting the value of *asymmetric w* follows a similar framework to traditional *Cohen's w*, but specifically in the direction of the column variable. A value of 0 indicates no effect of the column variable on the row variable, while a value close to or greater than 1 indicates a strong effect. Cohen provided some indicator values, which we will retain in this paper (See Table 1):

Table 1: Equivalents of w_{cAsym} in terms of *OR*, Cohen's *d* and Asymmetric Cramer's *V*

Effect size	Very small	Small	Medium	Large	Very large	Huge
$w_{Asym} (c=2) / phi_{Asym}$	0.005	0.099	0.243	0.371	0.515	0.707
<i>OR</i>	1.018	1.440	2.477	4.268	8.816	37.663
<i>d</i>	0.010	0.200	0.500	0.800	1.200	2.000
Cramer's $V_{Asym} (c=3)$	0.004	0.070	0.172	0.262	0.364	0.500
Cramer's $V_{Asym} (c=4)$	0.003	0.057	0.140	0.214	0.297	0.408
Cramer's $V_{Asym} (c=5)$	0.003	0.050	0.122	0.186	0.258	0.354
Cramer's $V_{Asym} (c=6)$	0.002	0.044	0.109	0.166	0.230	0.316
Cramer's $V_{Asym} (c=7)$	0.002	0.040	0.099	0.151	0.210	0.289
Cramer's $V_{Asym} (c=8)$	0.002	0.037	0.092	0.140	0.195	0.267
Cramer's $V_{Asym} (c=9)$	0.002	0.035	0.086	0.131	0.182	0.250

Note: Own elaboration based on formulas obtained from (Borenstein *et al.* 2009, pp. 239), Rosenthal (1994), and (Cohen 1988, pp. 221).

It's interesting to note that the results of this effect size, as defined, are consistent with odds ratios in the case of 2x2 tables. Obviously, due to its calculation method, it's not possible to account for directionality since it will always show the higher value regardless of how the categories are coded. In this aspect, it differs from odds ratios, where directionality is indicated by the inverse. The strength of this coefficient lies in its asymmetry, so the final value will indicate how much it differs from the chosen marginal (in this case, the columns).

7. Converting Asymmetric Cohen's *w* into Asymmetric Cramer's *V*

Effect sizes are often deemed more interpretable when their range falls between 0 and 1. To achieve this, we can leverage the relationship between Cramer's *V* and Cohen's *w*:

$$Cramer's V = \frac{w_{Sym}}{\sqrt{k-1}} \quad (17)$$

Here, *k* represents the smaller value between the columns and rows of the contingency table. This is very clearly explained by Cohen (1988, pp.221) indicating that the maximum value of *w* is just $w = \sqrt{k-1}$, so that *Cramer's V* is simply a sort of normalization in which the minimum value is 0 and the maximum 1.

However, in the case of the Asymmetric Cramer's *V*, we can derive it analogously from:

$$Cramer's V_{cAsym} = \frac{w_{cAsym}}{\sqrt{c-1}} \quad (18)$$

Where *c* represents the number of columns (always considering that the independent variable is in the columns). Thus, we will now obtain a value between 0 and 1. This arises in both cases from the consideration that the maximum value must necessarily imply that all cases are concentrated in one of the cells o_{ij} .

8. Asymmetric chi-square

Another crucial aspect regarding the relationship between chi-square and Cohen's *w* can generally be expressed as follows:

$$\chi^2 = w^2 \cdot n \quad (19)$$

It can be generalized to the asymmetric case without difficulty by:

$$\chi_{cAsym}^2 = W_{cAsym}^2 \cdot n \quad (20)$$

Hence, we can derive an estimate of the chi-square under a different null hypothesis, extending beyond the concept of mere co-association between variables, and instead focusing on a hypothesis related to the margins, specifically those of the columns in this case. In this sense, we believe that this chi-square measure also contributes to addressing the improper use of traditional chi-square when seeking to understand the effect of one variable on another.

Like,

$$W_{cAsym} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{c} \left(\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(p_{1ij} - p_{0m_j})^2}{p_{0m_j}} \right)} \quad (21)$$

which can be written as:

$$W_{cAsym} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{c} \left(\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{\left(\frac{o_{ij}}{m_j} - \frac{m_i}{n} \right)^2}{\frac{m_i}{n}} \right)} \quad (22)$$

and by (20),

$$\chi_{cAsym}^2 = \frac{n}{c} \left(\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{\left(\frac{o_{ij}}{m_j} - \frac{m_i}{n} \right)^2}{\frac{m_i}{n}} \right) \quad (23)$$

This method calculates the *chi-square* statistic not under the traditional null hypothesis of independence, but under the null hypothesis of independence concerning the observed frequencies relative to one of the margins—in this instance, the columns representing the factor (or independent variable).

The *asymmetric chi-square* could have the capability to detect specific relationships between categorical variables that might not be evident with the traditional approach. This implies that it could potentially identify associations that are more subtle or complex, thus providing a more comprehensive understanding of the data structure.

Unlike traditional chi-square, which often assumes complete independence between variables, the asymmetric approach may provide a more nuanced specification in cases with representative samples, where the aim is to explore the potential effects of one variable on another.

Depending on the specific context, *asymmetric chi-square* can provide a more intuitive or meaningful interpretation of the relationships between categorical variables under study. This can help researchers better understand the nature of identified associations and make more informed decisions based on the analysis results.

This approach contrasts clearly with the homogeneity test, which requires a sample for each subgroup and where marginal distributions offer no meaningful insight. In the homogeneity test, the null hypothesis assumes no differences relative to an unknown population distribution, using a calculation identical to that of the independence test, as previously discussed. In this context, we propose a null hypothesis stating that each column (factor or independent variable) follows the same distribution as the marginal distribution, reflecting the population distribution.

9. Post Hoc Analysis for Asymmetric Associations

Let's now delve into another crucial aspect we find important. When utilizing an asymmetric w, our objective is to assess the comprehensive impact of one variable on another. However,

there are instances where our focus shifts to evaluating the influence of a specific category of the factor or independent variable on the dependent or response variable. This is where the goodness-of-fit procedure comes into play. Unlike the comprehensive examination of the entire table, this procedure involves conducting hypothesis tests and corresponding effect size calculations for each category of the factor or independent variable:

$$w_j = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r \frac{(p_{1ij} - p_{0mj})^2}{p_{mj}}} \quad (24)$$

$p_{1ij} = \frac{o_{ij}}{m_j}$. The subscript 1 in p_{1ij} is indicated as in Cohen to account for the alternative hypothesis, o_{ij} represents the observed frequency in each cell ij , and m_j is the marginal frequency of each column j in the contingency table.

$p_{0mj} = \frac{m_i}{n}$ represents the marginal probability of the contingency table in the column direction. The subscript 0 (in p_{0mj}), as indicated in Cohen's work (1988), is used to represent the null hypothesis, m_i denotes the marginal frequency of row i , which is the total sum of values in the same row, and n represents the total number of observations in the contingency table. r is the number of rows in the contingency table.

What we obtain in this way is now a set of w values, one for each category of the factor or independent variable. Each of the w_j values will indicate the effect size between the marginal of the factor or independent variable and each category of the variable.

Then by,

$$\chi_{jAsym}^2 = W_{jAsym}^2 \cdot m_j \quad (25)$$

We can calculate a goodness of fit for each category, which is exactly what we need. However, it's important to interpret the p-values correctly since we are conducting multiple *post hoc* tests. To do this, we can apply the Benjamini-Hochberg correction method, which offers a less conservative approach (though other methods could also be considered):

$$\alpha_{Benjamini-Hochberg} = \frac{\alpha \cdot i}{c} \quad (26)$$

Where: α is the accepted level of Type I error set by the researcher, i is the rank of the obtained p-values, and c is the number of categories for the independent variable.

This method facilitates a reliable hypothesis test for analyzing asymmetric contingency tables, enabling the assessment of the impact of each category of the independent variable on the dependent variable. However, establishing causality ultimately depends on the research design.

It is worth noting that the entire procedure could also be conducted by comparing not with the marginal distribution of the independent variable, but with a specific category of interest within that variable. In such cases, adjustments to the entire procedure would be necessary, and regarding the *post hoc* adjustment, a suitable approach should be employed that aligns with the nature of the test.

10. Confidence intervals

Confidence intervals for the asymmetric Cohen's w coefficient can be generated using various methods, including the bootstrap method, permutation tests, or the non-central chi-square parameter method, similar to traditional approaches. As an alternative, a normal approximation can also be utilized:

$$VAR_{W_{cAsym}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}}}{n} \quad (27)$$

Where $e_{ij} = \frac{m_i}{c}$, with m_i representing the sum of row i , and c as the number of columns.

The standard error $SE_{w_{cAsym}}$ can then be calculated as follows:

$$SE_{w_{cAsym}} = \frac{\sqrt{VAR_{w_{cAsym}}}}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (28)$$

Substituting the expression from $VAR_{w_{cAsym}}$, we get:

$$SE_{W_{cAsym}} = \frac{1}{n} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(o_{ij} - \frac{m_i}{c})^2}{\frac{m_i}{c}}} \quad (29)$$

What would constitute an approximate standard error for calculating the confidence interval of asymmetric Cohen's w .

11. Conclusions

While association coefficients such as *Goodman and Kruskal's Tau-y*, *Lambda*, and the *Uncertainty coefficient* each have their strengths and limitations in addressing asymmetry within contingency tables, we propose introducing a new asymmetrical effect size coefficient derived from *Cohen's* well-known symmetric *w coefficient*. This innovative approach aims to enhance statistical methodology by providing more precise tools for analyzing the complexities inherent in unique samples and asymmetric associations between two variables. Furthermore, we have developed an *asymmetrical chi-square coefficient* specifically designed to accommodate asymmetry within the alternative hypothesis.

As a complement, a technique based on goodness-of-fit testing has been proposed to identify, in terms of hypothesis testing and effect sizes, which category or categories of the factor variable (or independent) contribute for the eventual rejection of the null hypothesis in the contingency table. For this purpose, we suggest the use of *Cohen's w* measure, already established in the literature, to evaluate the effect size of the difference between the distribution of a category and the marginal distribution of the dependent variable, and the chi-square as a *post hoc* goodness-of-fit test measure for the marginal distribution of the dependent variable. To ensure robust conclusions, an appropriate *post hoc* adjustment, such as the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure or another suitable method, should be applied to control for false discovery rates when multiple comparisons are involved.

In summary, this study addresses the need to carefully consider asymmetry in the analysis of nominal qualitative variables in contingency tables, proposing new measures and techniques that can enhance the understanding and interpretation of results obtained in this context.

When comparing two or more samples to determine if they originate from the same population (i.e., if they have identical unknown distributions), it is advisable, as indicated in the literature, to use the *chi-square test of homogeneity*. However, if the goal is to analyze the effect of one nominal variable on another in the context of a single representative probabilistic sample, the most appropriate approach would be to apply the *asymmetric chi-square test* and *Cohen's asymmetric w*. However, note that such results do not establish causality conclusively. Furthermore, as abundantly suggested in the literature, we agree that the results of hypothesis tests should always be reported together with their effect sizes and their respective confidence intervals.

Please note that in an experimental context where various treatments are randomly applied to different balanced groups, the results will be the same whether we use the *chi-square test*, or the *asymmetric chi-square test*; *Cohen's w*, or *Cohen's asymmetric w*. This is because the experimental design controls the conditions, ensuring that any observed difference can be attributed to the treatments.

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